

Radoslaw Niewiadomski and Cigdem Beyan: Toward Modeling Commensal Interactions in Human Dyads,

Complete List of questionnaires

Part 1 - Me and commensality

Me and commensality

1. I do enjoy eating alone
(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

2. I enjoy eating in silence (independently whether I am with and without others)
(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

3. Overall, the commensality (eating together) is important to me
(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

4. I often feel a strain while eating meals with others
(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

5. When given the choice, I prefer to eat a meal alone
(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

6. When eating alone, I miss conversations with others, sharing everyday experiences, stories...
(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

7. When eating I tend not to interact with other persons around me (I focus on food)
(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

8. When eating alone, I miss having company

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

9. Eating or drinking with others makes me uncomfortable

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

10. I enjoy eating with others and chatting

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

11. What are reasons for you to prefer to eat alone?

Open question

12. What are reasons for you to prefer to eat in company?

Open question

Frequency of eating

13. In the last 6 months, how often did you eat alone (on average)?

(Nearly Never) 1 2 3 4 5 (Nearly Always)

14. In the last 6 months, how often did you eat with someone else (on average)?

(Nearly Never) 1 2 3 4 5 (Nearly Always)

15. In the last 6 months, how often did you eat with someone else that you do not live with (on average)?

(Nearly Never) 1 2 3 4 5 (Nearly Always)

16. In the last 6 months, how often did you eat ONLINE (e.g., using skype, or zoom) with someone else (on average)

(Nearly Never) 1 2 3 4 5 (Nearly Always)

Use of Technology

17. Do you think that using devices such as camera/computer/tablet during meals is an acceptable practice?

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

18. Do you think that the presence of a camera/computer/tablet during the meal can make you feel uncomfortable?

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

19. Do you think that the presence of a camera/computer/tablet during the meal can make you feel stressed?

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

20. Do you think that the presence of a camera/computer/tablet during the meal can make you interact with others differently than usual (e.g., unnaturally)?

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

Part 2 - Strength of relationship

a) Inclusion of Other in the Self (IOS) Scale

A. Aron, E. N. Aron, M. Tudor, and G. Nelson. 1991. Close relationships as including other in the self. Journal of Personality and Social Psychology 60, 2 (1991), 241–253.

b) Quality of Relationships Inventory (QRI)

Gregory Pierce, Irwin Sarason, and Barbara Sarason. 1991. General and Relationship-Based Perceptions of Social Support: Are Two Constructs Better Than One? Journal of personality and social psychology 61 (12 1991), 1028–39. doi:10.1037/0022-3514.61.6.1028

Part 3 - Before the meal (PRE_Q)

Before the meal

Let's focus now on the person you will eat with soon. In the remaining questionnaire, we will refer to your interaction partner by "person X".

1. How long did you know each other with person X?

Open question

2. My feelings/attitude towards person X before this meeting is...

(Very Negative) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 (Very Positive)

3. In the least 6 months, how often did you eat together with person X?

(Nearly Never) 1 2 3 4 5 (Nearly Always)

4. I am happy to meet right now person X

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

5. I feel stressed before meeting now with person X

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

6. I think that feelings/attitude of person X towards me before this meeting is...

(Very Negative) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 (Very Positive)

Part 4 - After the meal (POST_Q)

How do I evaluate this specific commensal experience with person X.

In this questionnaire, please focus only on the experience that you have just participated.

1. In general, I would rate this experience...

(Very Negative) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 (Very Positive)

2. I liked the food I ate

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

3. My feelings/attitude towards person X after this meeting is...

(Very Negative) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 (Very Positive)

4. My feelings/attitudes regarding the setup (e.g., eating while being watched/recorded, being in an experimental setting, etc.) area...

(Very Negative) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 (Very Positive)

5. I really enjoyed this meeting with person X

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

6. This meeting made me feel closer to person X

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

7. I was engaged fully during this interaction

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

8. I interacted naturally (as usual) during this meeting

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

9. I felt uncomfortable during this meeting

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

10. I felt relaxed during this meeting

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

11. I felt irritated/frustrated during this meeting because of the behavior of person X

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

12. I felt irritated/frustrated by the setup (e.g., eating while being watched/recorded, being in an experimental setting, etc.)

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

13. The conversation with person X was enjoyable

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

14. The conversation with person X was fluent (i.e., there were no long pauses, incomprehension, misunderstandings, interruptions etc.)

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

15. It was a weird experience

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

16. I would repeat the same experience again with person X

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

17. I would repeat the same experience again with a different interaction partner

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

18. The presence of the electronic devices (e.g., camera, computer) disturbed me / (was a problem for me)

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

19. I think that feelings/attitude of person X towards me after this meeting is...

(Very Negative) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 (Very Positive)

20. I think person X really enjoyed this meeting

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

21. I think person X was engaged fully during this interaction

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

22. I think person X interacted naturally (as usual) during this meeting

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

23. I think person X felt uncomfortable during this meeting

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

24. I think person X felt relaxed during this meeting

(Totally disagree) 1 2 3 4 5 (Totally agree)

25. My eating pace ("speed"?) was... than usual.

(Very Negative) 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 (Very Positive)

26. Which aspects of this meeting did you enjoy particularly, if any ?

Open question

27. Which aspects of this meeting did you not enjoy particularly, if any ?

Open question